

Petrological Analysis of Igneous Rocks Exposed in North Eastern Part of Pyingyitaung, Singu Township, Mandalay Region

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Abstract

The research area is situated in the 18 km east of Singu Township, Mandalay Region, and covers about 28 km². This area lies between Latitude: 22° 32' 50" to 22° 36' 40" N and Longitude: 96° 08' 40" to 96° 11' 30" E in one inch topographic no. 93B/2. This area is mainly composed of Lower Tertiary intrusive igneous rocks such as leucogranite, tourmaline granite, foliated granite, biotite microgranite and pegmatite, which intruded into the medium to high grade Mogok metamorphic rocks. The granitic rocks belong to the acid clan and S-type with sedimentary origin. The liquidus temperature can be estimated for granitic rocks as between 650°C – 690°C. The granitic rocks of the research area may crystallize at depth between 21 km and 23 km. Economically prominent gold mineral deposits occurred in the northeastern part of research area. Granitic rocks in the research area are used for foundation as construction and road materials.

Introduction

Location and Size

The research area lies in Singu Township, Mandalay Region and is situated at the NE of Pyingyitaung. It is situated approximately 18 km east of Singu. It lies between latitude: 22° 32' 50" to 22° 36' 40" N, longitude: 96° 08' 40" to 96° 11' 30" E in one inch topographic map no. 93 B/2. The area measures about 4 km in E-W and 7 km in N-S direction and the area coverage is approximately 28 km². Location map of the research area is shown in Fig.1.

Fig.1 Location map of the research area

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Methods of Study

The research work includes field study and laboratory investigation.

1. Aerial photographs and satellite images were used for lithologic boundaries, fracture alignments and faults.
2. Geological mapping was carried out by using UTM map, GPS, Brunton compass and geological hammer etc.
3. Detailed petrographic studied of representative samples by using petrological microscope in the laboratory.
4. XRF and available analytical techniques were applied for mineralogical and petrological studies.

Nature of Rock Exposures

The study area is mainly composed of five granitic rocks contain leucogranite, foliated granite, tourmaline granite, biotite microgranite and pegmatite which intruded into the metamorphic rocks. These units are well exposed at the eastern and southern parts of the research area.

Petrography of the Igneous Rocks

Leucogranite (Field Description)

It is usually medium to coarse-grained, granular texture and essentially composed of felsic mineral and sometime shows graphic texture. The rock shows yellowish brown color on weathered surface and usually white color on fresh surface. Tourmaline granite occurs as small exposures and it cannot be mapped. It is intruded into the gneiss unit, Fig.2b.

Microscopic description

It shows granular texture and essentially composed of orthoclase, perthite, quartz and plagioclase. Quartz occurs as anhedral grains and especially intergrowth with plagioclase feldspar showing myrmekitic texture, Fig.3a. Orthoclase is more abundant mineral in thin section and especially occurs as untwined and some are altered to sericite. Perthite occurs as subhedral grains shows perthitic texture Fig.3b, c. Plagioclase display polysynthetic twinning and subhedral.

Fig.2 (a) outcrop nature of leucogranite (b) tourmaline granite intruded into the gneiss.

Fig.3 (a) photomicrograph of myrmekite (Myr) texture in leucogranite, 10x, (b) flame perthite (Per), and (c) string perthite in leucogranite, 4x, (d) traverse cracks with subhedral prismatic tourmaline (Tur) crystal in tourmaline granite, 4x, Location: E-209400, N-2498700

Foliated granite (Field Description)

. Most of the outcrops are highly weathered. Foliated occurs as slightly foliated nature probably parallel orientation of biotite flake. In hand specimen, quartz, feldspar and dark brown color biotite can be easily recognized. It shows light gray color on fresh surface and buff and yellowish brown on weathered surface. It is highly jointed and it also intruded into the gneiss unit, Fig.4a.

Microscopic Description

Foliated shows slight foliation by biotite flakes. It is medium to coarse-grained, showing hypidiomorphic granular texture. It is chiefly composed of alkali feldspar, quartz, plagioclase and biotite. Biotite shows one set of perfect cleavage and some are altered to chlorite. Quartz shows anhedral grains and sometime shows undulatory extinction.

Biotite microgranite (Field Description)

It is medium-grained, brown on weathered surface and gray color on fresh surface. It displays exfoliation weathering features and well jointed nature. It is widely distributed in the entire area.

Microscopic Description

It is medium-grained, showing hypidiomorphic granular texture. It is mainly composed of alkali feldspar, quartz, plagioclase and biotite. Minor amount of accessory minerals are muscovite and zircon minerals. Orthoclase is the essential mineral and some orthoclase shows simple contact twin. Untwined orthoclase is more abundant than twinned orthoclase and string perthite are also noted, Fig.5f. Some orthoclases are altered to sericite.

Pegmatite dykes and veins (Field Description)

Pegmatite dykes and veins are commonly intruded throughout the area. Pegmatite has been intruded and cut across the previous rocks. They occurred as concordant nature and discordant dyke along joints and most of the pegmatites are enclosed in the metamorphic unit, Fig.4c, d. It is very coarse-grained and exhibits whitish color on both weathered and fresh surface. Tourmaline, garnet and muscovite minerals are observed by naked eye.

Microscopic Description

It shows hypidomorphic granular and pegmatitic texture. It is very coarse-grained and mainly composed of quartz, alkali feldspar, platy minerals of muscovite and minor amount of plagioclase. Other minerals such as tourmaline and garnet are present as common accessory minerals. Quartz occurs as large anhedral grain. It shows undulose extinction. K-feldspar includes orthoclase and perthites. Orthoclase forms as subhedral to anhedral grains. Muscovite and biotite occur as subhedral flakes. Small grains of garnet are observed and elongated long prismatic tourmaline crystals are found in a matrix of feldspar and quartz.

(a)

(b)

Fig.4 (a) slightly foliated nature of foliated granite Loc: E-209464, N-2501127, (b) highly jointed nature of biotite microgranite Loc: E-210268, N-2501691 (c, d) pegmatite dyke intruded into the migmatite Loc: E-209380, N-2501143

Fig.5 (a) the alteration of biotite to chlorite (chl) in foliated granite, (b) graphic texture of quartz in foliated granite, (c) zircon (zrn) and apatite (Ap) enclosed in orthoclase feldspar of biotite microgranite, (d) alteration of orthoclase (Or) in biotite microgranite, (e) parallel alignment of biotite (Bt) in biotite microgranite 4x, (f) string perthite (per) of orthoclase in biotite microgranite.

Fig.6 (a) traverse cracks with longitudinal section and (b) distinct polygonal outline of tourmaline (Tur) bearing pegmatite.

Table (1) Analysed sample, locations and chemical compositions (major oxides) of the granitic rocks of the study area.

Sample Name	A3	A6	F1	G1	G9	L11	P2
	Biotite microgranite	Biotite microgranite	Biotite microgranite	Foliated granite	Foliated granite	Leucogranite	Pegmatite
Locality	E: 209654 N:2502300	E: 210435 N:2500716	E: 207768 N:2500191	E: 210225 N:2496821	E: 209559 N:2500918	E: 209400 N:2498700	E: 210030 N:2501759
Symbol	◆	◆	◆	▲	▲	■	●
SiO ₂	67.162	68.539	71.676	69.054	76.544	75.046	68.55
TiO ₂	1.433	0.703	0.302	0.271	0.056	0.741	0.56
Al ₂ O ₃	13.175	12.981	12.544	13.169	11.487	12.508	18.08
Fe ₂ O ₃	2.167	2.062	1.477	2.118	0.774	1.924	0.34
MnO	0.027	0.014	0.013	0.019	0.065	0.047	0.076
MgO	3.675	3.393	2.539	3.17	0.805	0.794	0.15
CaO	0.774	0.529	0.356	0.36	0.064	0.443	0.102
Na ₂ O	1.953	1.549	1.186	1.475	2.65	2.861	4.08
K ₂ O	3.495	4.654	7.221	5.323	5.569	3.481	3.81
P ₂ O ₅	0.083	0.024	0	0.06	0.023	0.133	0.18
Total	93.944	94.448	97.314	95.019	98.037	97.978	95.928

Fig.7 ACF diagram for the granitic rocks of the study area (After Hine et.al, 1978)
Molar ratio: A = Al₂O₃-Na₂O-K₂O, C = CaO, F = Fe₂O₃ + MgO

Conclusion and Discussion

The research area is mainly composed of leucogranite, tourmaline granite, foliated granite, biotite microgranite and pegmatite, which intruded into the medium to high grade Mogok metamorphic rocks. Petrographically, almost all the granitic rocks are medium to coarse-grained, hypidiomorphic granular texture. High SiO₂ content up to 76.54%, normative corundum > 1%, low Na₂O content < 2.86% and lack of normative magnetic are characteristics. Therefore, the granitic rocks in the area are S-type nature. Moreover, ACF diagram suggests that the granitic rocks of the study area are S-type. The liquids temperature can be estimated for granitic rocks as between 650°C – 690°C and crystallized at depth between 21km and 23km. The research area is considered to be emplaced in the Mesozone. In the northeastern part of research area, gold mineralization occurred as both primary and secondary deposit. Granitic rocks in the research area are crushed and chipped in various sizes, and then used for foundation as construction and road materials.

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